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**THE STUDY OF PREFERRED TOY CATEGORIES FOR CHILDREN WITH
DIFFERENT TEMPERAMENTS**

Yi-he Li / Min-yuan Ma / Wei-chen Li

Ph.D. student, Department of Industrial Design, National Cheng Kung University /
Associate Professor, Department of Industrial Design, National Cheng Kung University /
Kindergarten principal of Ben-gang elementary school
yuhelee@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

It is through playing games that children learn as they develop and grow up. Toys are important tools, and children can learn and grow from playing by using toys as teaching aids. Besides, every child has a different natural "temperament". Children with different temperaments need different teaching aids in their development. This study aims to identify the preferred toy categories for children with different temperaments.

This study uses The Carey Temperament Scales to divide preschool children into different groups, and select sample toys which is representative of each toy categories. To build the relationship between preference for toy categories and children with different temperaments, ANOVA Analysis, and LSD Multiple Comparisons would be used to analyze the research data.

Research result shows: children have different preference for toy categories, and children with different temperaments shows different preference for different toy categories.

Keywords: temperament.toy. preference

INTRODUCTION

With improvement of technology and the trend toward fewer children, requirement of children have been taken seriously gradually. Various kinds of expensive toys are there in the market, but not all of them are good for stimulating children's ability development. Some of the toys are only even decoration, or they are only designed with a couple of ways to play with which will lose players' curiosity soon. Under the circumstance of not long enough of playing time, children will not be able to develop

different type or level of game content through deep exploration. (Johnson, Christie, & Peckover,1988) Thus, for adults, especially for preschool education workers like kindergarten teachers or babysitters, they should pay more attention on the principle of the right age, the right ability, and the right personality between children and toys when they are picking toys for children. According to Piaget's game theory, (Piaget, 1962) Children who are at different phase of cognitive development will play games with different ways, and, in turn, games simultaneously reflect children's level of development at the moment. Besides of the cognitive development differences, each child was also born with different kinds of temperament. The definition of temperament is that it is a natural born, unique behavior pattern which stimulates internal or external reaction. It has nothing to do with IQ or future achievement, but it will affect infants' personality development.

Children with different temperaments need different teaching aids in their development. It would help to improve learning effects if adults timely provide children with help and guide. To promote effective learning and in order to stimulate their interest in games, it is important to select appropriate toys for the children with different temperaments. To achieve the above targets, this study aims to identify the preferred toy categories for children with different temperaments.

LITERATURE REVIEW

GAME THEORY

According to Cognitive-developmental theory of Piaget, children gain knowledge through internalization, adjustment, and construction of

individually contact with surrounding environment. However, during infant phase, a game is life, and life is a game. Toys have become a powerful tool to facilitate children's growth and learning. Piaget had divided children's cognitive development into 4 phases which are sensorimotor, preoperational, concrete operation, and formal operation phase. By explaining toys with perspective of cognitive development, he thought that cognitive development would affect children's games playing behaviors and divided those behaviors into three phases which are Practice play, Symbolic play, and Game with rules. After that, Smilansky, based on Piaget's categorization, revised cognitive games into four types. He changed Practice play with Functional play, and added Constructive play between Practice play and Symbolic play. He also changed symbolic play with Dramatic play. The last one remained Game with rules.

The four phases which cognitive development would experience are kind of gradual and continuous ones. Performance of each phase will be different depending on individual difference, but order of each phase will maintain the same.

DEVELOPMENTAL THEORY OF VYGOTSKY

zone of proximal development

The zone of proximal development, often abbreviated ZPD, is the difference between what a learner can do without help and what he or she can do with help. a child follows an adult's example and gradually develops the ability to do certain tasks without help. the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance, or in collaboration with more capable peers.

Scaffolding

Scaffolding is a process through which a teacher or more competent peer helps the student in his or her ZPD as necessary, and tapers off this aid as it

becomes unnecessary, much as a scaffold is removed from a building during construction.

Infants are born with independent performance and assisted performance during their growing process. In Vygotsky's scaffolding theory, he points out that children are able to stimulate their learning potential during the process of learning through games playing if there are adults aside to offer proper resource and assistance. For children of kindergarten level, the media which can stimulate learning potential is through adults offering proper games and toys.

TEMPERAMENT OF CHILDREN

Temperament has been recognized as an important factor in general social functioning and competence, including behavior with peers and peer acceptance for preschool to elementary school children and adolescents. Common dimensions of temperament based on the Thomas, Chess, and Birch (1977) model include (1) activity level; (2) rhythmicity; (3) approach-withdrawal; (4) adaptability; (5) reaction intensity; (6) quality of mood; (7) threshold; (8) distractibility; (9) persistence.

More recent work utilizing a psychobiological approach (Rothbart & Bates, 2006) views a child's temperament as constitutionally based individual differences in reactivity and regulation, influenced by heredity, maturation, and experience. The reactivity domain identified by Rothbart and Bates encompasses many of the attributes of the Thomas et al. model, including activity level, rhythmicity, approach-withdrawal, adaptability, intensity and quality of mood, and sensory threshold.

The infants-temperament meter used in the present research takes this version as a revising standard. After evaluating grade of each dimension according to the infants-temperament meter, we are able to understand children's behavior reaction trend within each dimension. The present research will use the infants-temperament meter to evaluate children's performance, and divided children into different temperamental groups to discuss their preferences and durability toward toys.

CATEGORIZATION OF TOYS

There are various kinds of toys, and so are categorizing standards. The present research will categorize toys according to Piaget's game theory of cognitive development:

- (1) symbolic play materials
- (2) Fluid-construction play materials
- (3) Structured-construction play material
- (4) Sensori-motor play materials
- (5) Sign play-numbers and letters

The present research will utilize Piaget's game theory to divide toys into 5 categorizations and pick out the most typical toy of each categorization to be our experimental sample according to experts' opinion.

METHOD AND PROCEDURES

PARTICIPANTS

Participants are 23 students from advanced and intermediate class of kindergarten of Taoyuan County Ben-Gang Elementary School. Their age range is between 4 and 6 years old. Carers of the students, which are kindergarten teachers, are required to fill out questionnaire of children temperament.

EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLE

We take Piaget's game theory as the basis of toys categorization and consult experts' opinion to choose the most typical toy of each categorization to be the experimental sample which are listed below:

1. Sensory action game: Game set that physical ability is integrated by senses, and hereafter it is defined as a physical toy.
2. Symbolic role-playing game: Game set of kitchen role-playing, and hereafter it is defined as a doll toy.
3. Structural construction game: Building blocks, and hereafter it is defined as a building block toy.
4. Fluid construction game: Wheat clay and clay tools, and hereafter they are defined as a clay toy.
5. Number-symbol game: Number board and pokers, and hereafter they are defined as a number toy.

figure1. experimental samples

EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT

We decorate a kindergarten classroom as a experimental game zone and call it a "happy corner" in order to match up our activities which proceed in the corner. 5 experimental sample toys which represent Piaget's game theory are placed in the corner, and toy amount of each categorization must be enough for participants. Jigsaw mats of different color are used to separate playing space of each game. Taping equipments are set in the classroom to record experiment process which is convenient for data collection and data analysis afterward.

figure2. happy corner

OBSERVATION AND RECORDING

6 to 8 children are arranged to enter the experimental game zone- happy corner. Corner staying time for each group is around 40 minutes. Toys which are picked by children and their playing time length are recorded on experimental data sheet. Total experimental number of times is 23. Experimental data of 7 times for each participant are obtained.

The purpose of this phase is to utilize the decoration of happy corner to allow children to pick games and toys according to their preference. Through recording toy playing time as quantitative analyzing data, we discuss whether different kinds of toy will have different level of durability toward children.

DATA ANALYSIS

ANALYSIS OF PARTICIPANTS

Through result of the questionnaires, we utilize cluster analysis to sort out children’s temperament clusters. The sorting results are listed as below:

Extrovert type: 4 children, Their activity level is higher than approach, their attention span is a little too short, and they are easy to be noticed

Unique type: 4 children, Their activity level is high but short on attention span, and their persistence and adaptability are comparatively lower.

Hyperactive children, schizophrenia, slow learners of learning and language are included in this type.

Serene type: 4 children, Their activity level, approach, and intensity of mood are low, but their persistence is the highest. They are more focused to deal with their own business and rare to express their opinion or thought.

Ordinary type:11 children, their adaptability is the highest among all clusters, but they perform ordinarily on the rest dimensions. The most children are in this type.

DURABILITY ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLE

The analysis of the present experiment is to individually measure playing time from the first to the seventh experiment. Our purpose is to understand whether differences of durability exist or not among toys through the toys choice every time from the beginning to the end of the experiment.

Figure3.

At first, the toy types children chose were not consistent. Playing time of physical toy is obviously higher than other toys. During mid-later phase of the experiment, children’s choices of toys were more consistent which means that the phenomenon of obvious longer playing time of particular toy did not exist. As increasing of experimental number of times, the playing time of physical toy gradually decreased; On the contrary, no one picked number game at the beginning, but its playing time obviously increased during later phase of the experiment which anticipates that different level of durability do exist among different toys.

This phase also utilize regression curve estimation to draw out durability curves of 5 experimental toy samples during 7 times of experiment. Analysis purpose is to judge whether, as a whole, experimental samples have durability or not according to the trend of the regression curve.

Physical toys

The curve regression mode of physical toys corresponding to the N time of experiment is a log curve. When the number of times of experiment gets higher, the time that children play with physical toys gets shorter. In other words, physical toys will be less and less attractive to children as the experiment is approaching toward its end. As for the result of the present research, physical toys do not have durability.

Figure4. the curve regression mode of physica toy

Clay toys and number toys

No matter during early or later phase, the time that children play with clay toys and number toys remains stable which means that these two toys have a certain level of durability.

Figure5. the curve regression mode of clay toy

Figure6. the curve regression mode of number toy

Role-playing toys and building blocks toys

As for the time that children play with role-playing and building blocks toys, its increasing amount of later phase is larger than early phase which means that role-playing toys have the durability which can attract children continue to play with.

Figure7. the curve regression mode of role-playing toy

Figure8. the curve regression mode of building blocks toy

Brief summary

According to the analysis above, we can find out that among the 5 chosen toy samples, the playing time of building blocks and role-playing toys at the beginning is comparatively shorter but increasing during the later phase. However, the playing time of clay and number toys approximately remains the same. The above 4 toys persistently attract children to keep playing with. Nevertheless, as for the physical toys, although it has the specialty to attract children and its playing time is the longest during the early phase of the experiment, however, as the number of times of experiment increases, its playing time becomes shorter and shorter which means that physical toys do not have durability among these experimental samples.

ANOVA ANALYSIS OF TEMPERAMENT CLUSTERS TOWARD TOYS PLAYING TIME

According to the analysis result in the last chapter, physical toys are less durable to children in the present experiment. Thus, we will only discuss clay, number, role-playing, and building blocks toys. The present research utilizes one-way ANOVA to analyze playing time of children from different temperament clusters toward different toys: Role-playing toy has significant p value for children from different temperament clusters ($P=0.011 < 0.05$), and building blocks toy has near significant p value ($P=0.056 < 0.1$).

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Clay toy	Between Groups	4663.705	3	1554.568	.329	.804
	Within Groups	89754.295	19	4723.910		
	Total	94418.000	22			
Number toy	Between Groups	7444.327	3	2481.442	1.333	.293
	Within Groups	35372.977	19	1861.736		
	Total	42817.304	22			
Doll toy	Between Groups	28558.120	3	9519.373	4.885	.011
	Within Groups	37024.750	19	1948.671		
	Total	65582.870	22			
Block toy	Between Groups	1778.705	3	592.902	3.014	.056
	Within Groups	3737.295	19	196.700		
	Total	5516.000	22			

table1. the analysis result of ANOVA

From Scheff's multiple comparison we can find out that the playing time of role-playing toys for children of unique type is obviously longer than children of ordinary type. Moreover, from the result of LSD multiple comparison, the playing time of role-playing toys for children of unique type is obviously longer than other children. However, the playing time of building blocks toy for children of serene type is obviously longer than children of extrovert type.

CONCLUSION

Role-playing toy is categorized as a "symbolic game plaything" in children development. This type of toy can facilitate children's social behavior and improve individual ability to efficiently deal with problems of interpersonal relationship. Unique type children's playing time of role-playing toy is obviously higher than ordinary type children, and its possible reason is that the integration level among groups of unique type children is easily decreased by their physical and mental status factors. Due to lower level of socialization, children are more easily attracted by symbolic game plaything and fulfill their cognitive and personality developmental expectation and imagination through behaviors of role-playing. During

the symbolic role-playing game, children's preference of concrete toys is in inverse proportion to their socialization level which means that the younger or lower socialized the children are, the more they will be attracted by concrete toys. Ways to play building blocks toys belongs to a experience of solving problems. From the perspective of cognitive motivation construction, as infants solve problems or have breakthrough, it means that the infants have obtained cognitive function of higher level. It requires higher attention when playing with building blocks toys, thus, it is easier to attract serene type children whose activity level is lower, attention span is shorter, and persistent level is higher.

Research result shows: children have different preference for toy categories, and children with different temperaments shows different preference for different toy categories. Based on the theory of child temperament, this study builds the relationship between child temperament and toy categories. It provides childhood educator a reference to choose toys, but also a design guideline for toy designer.

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